

College of Engineering and Computational Sciences

Department of Architecture and Urban Planning

**Small-Scale Mill-houses in the Urban Neighborhoods of Addis Ababa and
their Sustainable application: The case of Millhouses in Yeka Sub-city**

BSc Thesis:

This thesis is submitted to College of Engineering and Computational Sciences, Department of Architecture and Urban Planning of Unity University for partial fulfillment of all requirements of Bachelor of Science in Architecture and Urban Planning.

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August 2020

Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

Declaration

I declare that, this thesis prepared for the partial fulfillment of all the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Architecture and Urban Planning entitled “**Small-Scale Mill-houses in the Urban Neighborhoods of and their sustainable application: The case of Millhouses in Yeka Sub-city**“ is My original research work prepared in an effort with the close advice and guidance of my adviser. I also declare that this thesis has not been presented in any university and all sources that I have used or quoted have been indicated and acknowledged by means of complete references.

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Certification

Here with I state that Nehemiah Shiferaw has carried out this research work on the topic entitled “**Small-Scale Mill-houses in the Urban Neighborhoods of and their sustainable application: The case of Millhouses in Yeka Sub-city**“: under my supervision and it is sufficient for the partial fulfillment for the award of BSc degree in Architecture and Urban Planning.

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Abstract

This research assesses the architectural quality perception of small-scale mill-houses in the inner-city neighborhoods of Addis Ababa at Yeka Sub-city. Taking Wossen neighborhood as a local case study. The study has employed 3 mill owners, 7 mill workers, and 35 mill house users as a numbers of sample size population in an in-depth interview, structured questionnaires, and field on observation to collect primary and secondary data. On the areal contexts, the study tried to observe the 26 mills architectural state in an area of 3.1 Sq.km urban space around Wesson neighborhood. According to Ethiopian Urbanization Review (2015), Addis Ababa have a maximum density of 30,000 people/km². And this makes the study to have a target of 93,000 peoples living in diverse residential urban space.

The study evaluated mill houses current architectural character with a central aim to study the sustainable roles of mills in the city. Adding on this, it discusses the role of architecture as a discipline responsible for the structuring of physical space in the city in response to economic, environmental, and social challenges faced in the contextual reality of ensuring food security in urban areas. It provides a pool of information on sustainable applications of architectural advancements our mill-houses need in the inner-city neighborhoods of Addis Ababa. During the research, personal interviews, and discussions with mill owners over mill houses' problems had led to the learning of the architectural needs of these physical structures and it suggested the needs of addressing those problems architecturally. Along with this, by choosing one purposely selected mill house, and by examining the architectural quality of the mill, it identified that constructed structures for milling services shown lower architectural quality. Plus, the satisfaction level where one mill house should provide to mill owners, workers, and customers have degraded by their current architectural and structural conditions. This part is furtherly discussed in the second chapter.

The results of this research show that there is an opportunity in developing the architectural aspects of mills in our urban neighborhoods. There is also strength, and opportunity that helps the idea of industrializing the milling services in to modernity. These kinds of privately owned businesses have good potential on their reliability of food security, and accountability. What is needed is modernizing the milling industry and changing small-scale milling services in to middle-scale and large-scale milling industries. And introduce a patented and labeled end products by the government. To regulate and study around milling production processes.

Therefore, this study calls for creating awareness on the management of mills. And discuss issues over the roles of architects in sustainable community development to bring solutions that are means of resolving societal problems related to food and its production process in Addis Ababa. Taking in advance that mills are physical structures of an urban area that should be productive enough for the higher demand of the growing number of the urban population. Concerning the people's need for milling service, as well as considering to compete with the modern food processing industry witnessed in the contemporary world without losing the community's own culture and identity. As a result, the study tries to find an alternative solution that integrates the implementation of sustainability in the designing of mills for the quality life of the community living in urban areas. Moreover, mill owners should fulfill the needs of workers, the expectations of their customers, for serviceability, and quality of life. Therefore, involving in the construction of standardized mill houses that respects the food grinding processes, and also the architectural aspects of the physical environment in the city.

Methods to advance the Small-Scale Mill houses lies on stakeholders who need sustainability in their community, and suggest that mill houses should get proper attention from private, governmental, and non-governmental stakeholders aside from only preparing industrial zones. Above and beyond, work for reassuring the provision of different types of financial and technical skills over the planning programs of constructing standardized large-scale mill houses. To improve their architectural quality, as well as to scale up their production services to provide proper milling facility for the community within the urban neighborhoods. Even at a larger scale of considering mills as long-lasting strategic projects that supplement the GTP of the city, and the competitiveness of Addis Ababa.

Key Words:

Mill houses, Sustainability, sustainable community, Architectural quality, Architectural advancement, Urban population, Food consumption, modern food processing industry

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I would like to thank HOLY SPIRIT for HIS favor to study in UNITY UNIVERSITY and for all HIS miraculous help in all of my difficulties and needs throughout my Five years of enrollment to earn the degree in Bachelor of Science in Architecture and Urban Planning. I am forever thankful for my everyday counselor, comforter, and to all the wisdom HE gave me, though many times I have had doubts and questioned if I've made the right decision to learn Architecture and wanted to give up, but, HE has made it possible for me to endure.

My sincere appreciation goes to my Supervisor, Architect Woudnesh Birru for the critical questions, comments, and unreserved encouragement she showed me to select this topic. I am grateful to her guidance throughout the thesis work by making possibilities to communicate in the programmed consultations we had using digital methods in this Covid-19 Pandemic.

My genuine appreciation extends to my Mother Tenaye, and my Father Shiferaw for their love, prayer, and encouragement, and my special thanks go to my brothers Henok and Nahom. I cannot forget their kind support. I owe you my deepest gratitude. This study would not have been possible without these people's support and encouragement.

Nehemiah Shiferaw

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Abbreviation and Acronyms

AACPPO – Addis Ababa city planning project office

CSA- Central Statistics Agency

IFPRI - International Food Policy Research Institute

KG- Kindergarten

NGO - Nongovernmental organizations

WPR- World Population Review

USDA- United States Department of Agriculture

Small-Scale Mill-houses in the Urban Neighborhoods of and their sustainable application:
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CHAPTER ONE

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

The processing of food grain plays a vital economic role in countries that are yet developing; in these countries, particularly in urban areas, low-income groups are not able to carry out the processing of agricultural products. They find that a mill is a primary element in their dietary life for grinding edible grains. This had led to why millhouses are accounted for the classical example of the choice of food processing technology (UNIDO 1986). It is because mills advantages and acceptability in Ethiopians food culture is plain. Currently, without a mill-house role and the traditional milling production process, it is hard, and inconvenient for the majority of the urban community, particularly to the low-income groups to have a daily balanced dietary life in the inner-city neighborhoods of Addis Ababa. Furthermore, physical structures such as mill houses, provide socioeconomic advantages for the community, and their high potential in safekeeping the food culture of the people makes them more required in the urban settlement.

The city of Addis Ababa is growing in number of populations. During the study period, according to WPR, it is estimated to be 4.8 million, and sources from CSA shows that the city is expected to double its population by 2030, and statistically in 2037 it is expected to reach 9.8 million with population growth rate of 3.8% / annum. This unprecedented urban population growth is on one side considered as an advantage of economic growth, but if not well managed, it could also worsen community well-being specially with regards to food security which relates to availability, accessibility, utilization and stability of food. Considering the relation between the four pillars of food security and the advantages of having mill houses in the city is furtherly discussed in the second chapter.

In general, if there is an expanding population size, it is a fact there will be a consistent growth of demand for milling services concerning the increase in food consumption. However, these physical structures have not been given the needed attention by the stakeholders, and also their services are inadequate in the face of this expanding population size. Degradation and neglect in their overall architectural progress has made mill houses questionable over their quality of service and their potential for meeting the demand of the growing population.

1.1.1. Socioeconomic attributes of mill houses

Millhouses have plenty of positive attributes for socio-economic activities within communities, which strengthens the idea of sustainable communities. Millhouses as a physical structure of one neighborhood, they are potentially working directly on safekeeping food culture. By being a means of preparing digestible grains of crops and cereals, pulses, and vegetables, which are related to the day to day dietary life of the people and their food culture, particularly to the low-income groups. Another reason for prevalent food and income insecurity is always tied to poverty. To mention one recent example, when communities living in the city of Addis Ababa, were passing through in critical situation like the pandemic Covid-19, particularly low-income groups in the community became depressed and faced other health-related problems. As the very recent research by Kalle, Gashaw and Alan (IFPRI, 2020), show in data that; poorer households are those who were extremely stressed during the pandemic when seen by household wealth index, regarding their dietary life. (Virtual seminar: COVID-19 and its impact on Ethiopia's agri-food system, food security, and nutrition) it also showed that households self-reported the aspect of the pandemic crisis to have impacted their life because of reasons such as unemployment/loss of income dominating by 34% percent. And another reason for the high cost and shortage of food among households in the urban areas of Addis Ababa became 18% and 4% respectively. It is here that regardless of the increase in price for use of grains such as *Teff*¹, that mill houses have given crucial help for the community by providing a long-time payment method for their customers in times of need for a loan. Such benefits can be seen in ways of indirect relation to social life yet, with a solid impression. It was seen repeatedly during the Covid-19 pandemic crisis where low-income groups bought grains through loans from local mill houses agreed only with an *Oral-Contract*². It is because of the deep-rooted social relation they have with the community and the growth of trust among the customers and the millhouse owners. When doing commercial activities, we need such kinds of social relationships among customers and service providers in times of *shock*³ in cities. This character is what makes millhouses unique and needed in the urban settlement. And unless this is available, the absence of these in social services will lead to a wide range of chronic conditions that may come along with the lack of proper dietary services. And due to economic limitations, the fear it causes especially, to the low-income groups in the urban is very high.

¹ Teff- Is one of the most important staple crops in Ethiopia, which is used for making the flat pancakes Injera.

² Oral- *Contract* is a contract, the terms of which have been agreed by spoken communication.

³ Shock- Is a single unpredictable event happening to a city (A.A, Ethiopia, Enhancing Urban Resilience (July, 2015).

Figure 1. Aspect of the corona crisis (Income and price effects dominate the self-reported pandemic impacts)

Source: IFPRI, image downloaded from (2020, P.5): <https://www.slideshare.net/essp2/covid19-and-its-impact-on-ethiopia-agrifood-system-food-security-and-nutrition>

1.2. Problem Statement

Despite mill houses benefits for social life, there is a low increase in their architectural advancement. And though they are serving the basic need of human beings (Food), they are lagging architecturally. Compared to the changes seen in the architectural character of the city, and the modernization of many services of the urban neighborhoods, mill houses did not get much attention by stakeholders. But it should have been the opposite happening, when situation such as rapid urbanization is tied to widespread food and income insecurity. Since mills are directly related to the basic needs of human life; lower-income groups and the destitute are dependent on mill house services for their daily food consumption. This problem does not merely relate only to concerns that focus on the community, but also the physical environment. Apart from community members, the built environment is also a fundamental component of every community. (Chansomsak, Sant & Vale, Brenda (2010). And in a rapidly urbanizing region, space (environmental space in an urban area) can be seen as one of the most basic contested resources (Zegeye C., Helawi S., UN Chronicle, n.d.). Any built environment should have a priority to be designed with efficiency to resolve societal problems in the urban settlement. Therefore, as a built environment in urban areas, mill houses need careful planning and design reconsiderations that are tangible. And this study will try to find out what alternative solution can stop the trend of neglect on these architecturally degrading small-scale mill houses.

1.3. Research Objectives:

1.3.1. General objective

The overall research objective of this paper is to describe and briefly analyze the topic of having millhouses in urban neighborhoods and to address their potential for boosting the socio-economic activities and also their benefits in safekeeping the food culture and the dietary life of the people. This research will also assess the design developments that mill houses need in order to increase the standard of their architectural aspect in the neighborhood by identifying customer's perception and satisfaction level of users about the mill house space, and evaluate the needs of the community (users of the end product.) Another major consideration is the state of workers in the mill. For example, to investigate the conditions of employed workers in mill houses and learn what they need by questioning their perception and satisfaction about the space. And within these primary objectives, there are two secondary objectives.

1.3.2. Specific objectives

First, to examine the current architectural situations of mill houses in relation to the three dimensions of sustainability; economic, social and environmental. Secondly to identify the main problems found during the research and give architectural solutions.

1.4. Research Questions

1. How can new innovative designs be created for small-scale mill houses that are integrated with the character of the neighborhood and the community?
2. How can we address the architectural problems of millhouses regarding space management challenged by the small land area permit for construction in the existing conditions of a neighborhood?
3. Are the mill houses in the city sustainable enough for the rapidly growing urban population and the growing demand of their service?
4. How to design a sustainable milling service for the growing urban population in the city?
5. Can a Milhouse be integrated with other related services in the neighborhood in order to engage with public participations and different stakeholders to create a sustainable society for the communities and to strengthen their social life and economic activities?
6. What knowledge can be gained through the research on the architectural developments of small-scale millhouses?

1.5. Scope of the Study

1.5.1. Thematic scope

The title of this research is (Small-Scale Mill-houses in the urban neighborhoods of Addis Ababa and their Sustainable application: The case of Millhouses in Yeka Sub-city). And this research is focused only on privately owned small-scale mill houses found in Addis Ababa. It aims to study about their socio-economic activities in the neighborhoods. It mirrors their potential in safekeeping food culture and their role in the urban settlement regarding food security. It also assesses their overall architectural quality by questioning their sustainability and by considering the city's pursuit for a sustainable development and tries to come up with an alternative design recommendation and conclusions.

1.5.2. Spatial scope

The study is limited to the geographic boundaries of Addis Ababa city and focuses at Yeka sub-city. Millhouses are found plentiful at older residential places, and very few around condominium housings and none in the modern real-estate housings. Because of this reason, it was necessary to study the availability, accessibility and economic activities of mills around the two types of urban settlement. So Wossen neighborhood and Ayat Tafo sites were chosen for the spatial scope of the case study.

1.6. Significance of study

The study will identify that to date, there are no relevant architectural studies on the local level, considering the topic of mill houses. That deals with the assessment of architectural quality perception and sustainable applications of small-scale mill-houses in Addis Ababa, particularly regarding the urban neighborhoods. The purpose of this paper, in this regard, is to contribute information for all stakeholders in the community, governmental and non-governmental organizations, policymakers, planners, and architects about mill houses role in the economic, environmental, and social dimensions of sustainability and that all stakeholders should work holistically to scale up small-scale mill houses to a larger scale of food production industry for the urban space and at large for the rural as well.

1.7. Research methodology

1.7.1. Selection of the Case Study Area

The location of the selected mill-house case study area is on the side of a local street (Fig. 3), located in the inner part of the neighborhood. This particular mill-house or locally known by its name as “Tolcha-Meda Wofcho-bet,” is situated in front of a kindergarten school. It is separated by 10-meter collector street from the KG. Also, the location of this mill is at the border to both Woreda 11 and Woreda 13. It is moderately a busy mill house in the neighborhood; since it has daily customers but faces challenges of attracting customers as there are also plenty of mill houses around the area. It also lacks ample area for parking and has Architectural problems to be addressed, such as worker’s space and standard of construction to list the least. Another potential of the study area is that its neighbor area is for kebele microfinance working space. And there are three locally constructed workshop buildings side by side and have been an area of the wood workshop and was in practice for several years when recently they are working on the production of food products such as injera and bread to give services for the community around which is discussed further in the “Local case study: Tolcha Meda Wofcho-bet” section. The reason for choosing this site, **Wosson** neighborhood as one example is because there is a criterion for finding relevant information. Plus, there are plenty of residential communities with good neighborhood character. And the number of millhouses that have a minimum of 5-20 years of age are many. Therefore, by studying these Millhouses and by taking the **Wosson** neighborhood as one example considering the above issues this thesis will be focusing on the assessment of millhouses’ architectural condition in the urban neighborhoods.

1.8. Methodological approach

The overall approach to the research is to examine the current problems seen on mill houses of the urban neighborhood and considering them as a physical structure that defines the community’s socio-economic activities. Thus, this paper will try to answer the questions raised while observing the current state of mill houses as investigated in the day to day usage of these milling services. Such as the architectural aspects of the millhouse, building conditions. Also, it will discuss their effect on the surrounding structures and their overall space utilization. During this research, it was difficult to compile a vast qualitative method of approach to the research mainly due to the current situation of the pandemic (Covid-19). Though, it will have a mixed type of research method which will integrate both the Quantitative method and the Qualitative method.

1.8.1. Quantitative method

The Quantitative methods will encompass the surveys on the millhouses and the data needed in the form of numbers. Such as the number of customers, peak hours of service throughout the day, and a specific land area of the current Millhouse to make generalizations on the later process of suggesting an innovative design approach solution. In consequence, this was done by a questionnaire which includes: multiple-choice questions with a Likert scale, and Yes or No questions of quantitative methods.

1.8.2. Qualitative method

And the Qualitative method will be mainly working on an in-depth exploration through interviews of willing customers in the neighborhood, the millowner and the workers at the mill house regarding their thoughts and experiences while getting services, their working and living conditions in the mill house respectively. The questions were raised specifically on issues of satisfaction on both working and living conditions in the millhouse, by asking respondents about the space utilization and customer feedback at the selected case study site in order to determine the generalizations of the later design recommendation and conclusions.

1.8.3. The Type of the Research

Thus, this research used a mixed type of research method which will integrate both the Quantitative method and the Qualitative method.

1.9. Data sources and method of data collection

During the research, in-depth interviews have been taken to identify the customer's emotions, feelings, and opinions regarding the architectural aspect of mill houses in their neighborhoods. Additionally, an online questionnaire had been conducted to have more insight toward end-product users of mill houses in Addis Ababa region, and their perception towards mill houses. There were 35 respondents, and the gathered answers were used for the research outcome. Concerning the interviews and questionnaire, it was only done with flexibility by leaving room for the generation of conclusions from customers (the community), mill owners, and also workers in the mill. Meaning generalization regarding innovative design solutions for millhouses was never from an individual perspective.

1.10. Limitation of the study

The limitation of the study includes a lack of compiled files or published researches on mill houses. Although some international researches and guidelines were helpful in the conducting of this research. But there were no available studies regarding the architectural design of mill house structures or published general design guidelines on the standards of planning, allocating, siting of a particular millhouse at the neighborhood level for the city of Addis Ababa. And also, there was no data available on how many millhouses are supposed to be in a radius of one-kilometer area for a neighborhood and standards of allocating mills in the urban settlements.

Besides, there was no compiled data or studies available on people's feedbacks or reactions regarding millhouse services. However, interviews were conducted with stakeholders who related to the aim of the research. And those who were directly connected to the milling services and food security in the city. A major problem which limited the gathering of data was on the process of physical interviews for the research. The main cause that hindered physical questionnaires for the case study was the reason for the Covid-19 pandemic because it was hard to find and gather rich and sufficient data using physical interviews and questionnaires. To tackle such barriers, online questionnaires were conducted, but continual interruption of internet services in the country due to political reasons. Such difficulties happened during the research that made limitations on the collected data not to be fully satisfactory for the research conclusion and final recommendations.

1.11. Research design

Figure 2. Research Design Diagram.

Source: Author's construction.

CHAPTER TWO

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Introduction

A mill-house, as defined by the Oxford Dictionary on LEXICO, it is a building in which milling or grinding is carried on; a building (especially a dwelling house) adjoining a mill. Particularly here in Ethiopia, they are mostly found in the older neighborhoods (*seffer*⁴) of the capital city of Addis Ababa. Currently, during the study period, sources from the Addis Ababa Trade Bureau shows that there are 3,565 legally registered millhouses in Addis Ababa that are giving grinding services to communities (Addis Ababa Trade Bureau, 2020). Meanwhile, the physical realm of mill-houses, meaning their architectural condition is still doubtful and below the standard. Their construction technique has gone through different typologies depending on the availability of material for construction, budget, and the context of the mill owner. But, specifically, the housing typologies of millhouses in the inner neighborhoods of Addis Ababa include; the trend of constructing local shade structures such as using corrugated iron sheets, and wattle and daub (mud houses). Beyond the physical conditions of mill-houses, this study has observed that a mill-house has plenty of positive attributes for the sustainability of communities. Also, their role in the enhancement of socio-economic activities in an urban neighborhood is vital.

Any building that serves a purpose is vital for any economy, but also has a significant impact on the environment. A mill boosts economic activities between multiple stakeholders, but if not well managed and carefully designed, it will leave an impact on the environment. According to Peter, Ezekiel and Paul (2012, p. 18), ‘A building should not neglect environmental quality and human satisfaction in and around the built environment. Saving energy, and performing well only does not make it a sustainable product, but it should bring positive affect on the occupants’ comfort and enhance productivity’. That is why having a conceptual framework or known as the ‘sustainable triple bottom line principle’, helps to earn sustainability in the designing and constructing of any building. Since it works for the creation of an appropriate balance between economic, social and environmental issues and involves a design for human adaptation and sustainability.

¹ Seffers- Is an Amharic term as to say ‘neighborhoods’

Figure 3. Vitality of any building, key management service and environmental impact

Source: Author's construction.

2.2. Theories, concepts and definitions

2.2.1. Sustainability

Sustainability itself is a process that encompasses the three dimensions of economic, environmental, and social (Cassen 1987). These three dimensions of sustainability shape the community living together at a specific place, which leads the community to create a sustainable development strategy seeking an economic development that later benefits the local environment and quality of life (Center of Excellence for Sustainable Development, 1999, n.p.). Sustainability reaches the community through those three dimensions. But as a contact point, it needs peoples who are willing to dedicate their ethics to the idea of sustainability. As every individual has a role in the sustainability of communities, Architects can take the lead by integrating the concepts of sustainable community development through their actions both as citizens and also as professionals (Chansomsak, Sant & Vale, Brenda, 2010).

To emphasize more on subjects of sustainability, and sustainable community development, sustainable community development is the outcome of a holistic view of a community, embracing nature, culture, and politics, as well as the economy within a sustainable-concept. Chansomsak, Sant & Vale, Brenda (2010) also argue that, over a while, the works of the architectural profession support the physical development of a community. It may vary from design to planning, but as professionals, the relationships between people and place (any space in the urban area) as well as people and people (their social life) are the responsibility and concerns for architects to consider these in their concepts. Encompassing these concepts with their thoughtful design or planning, can determine a community's movement from 'weak' to 'strong' sustainability.

2.2.2. Sustainability as a concept

Sustainability as a concept has been in practice through architecture and has grown to fame in the current time as well. Architects, designers, engineers, and others involved in the building industry have kindled their zeal for a sustainable world. In the process of building, they have given a unique opportunity to cut back environmental impact through the implementation of sustainability objectives at the planning development stage of a building project. It explains about having a common goal while the design development is at the micro-level (specific level) of the project. This common objective addresses that buildings are designed to reduce the overall impact of the built environment on human health, quality of life, and the natural environment as well.

According to Addis and Talbot (2001); Brownhill and Rao (2002), environmental protection, social well-being, and economic prosperity are the three main pillars governed under the concept of sustainable construction. And those three main pillars have their points of concern. Such as environmental protection is concerned with keeping the built and the natural environment healthy for people to live. Concerning this, if we evaluate the construction of our current mill houses, their built physical structures show that in the built environment they are not handled properly, and reversely they have their impact on the environment. That environment can represent any neighborhood that mills are located. And if evaluated under the pillar of social well-being, their sustainability comes in question because of their neglect on considering human feelings, satisfaction, safety, and comfort. The two points of safety and comfort relate directly to the users (workers and customers) health. That makes social well-being to be upfront while considering the concept of sustainable construction of physical structures. The third pillar of economic sustainability relates to the overall monetary gains it contributes to all communities living in the built and the natural environment.

Using this broad and complex concept many architects and designers have designed and constructed projects that are sustainable. These sustainable projects have their own defining features, they are designed, built, renovated, operated or reused in an ecological and resource efficient manner. Though by putting in considerations that, the appropriate technologies are always dependent on the place, local supply, labor skills, and time availability of that particular area, the following points are mentioned for architects to put in consideration whenever they plan for a sustainable building.

- Pollution prevention
- Improved indoor air quality
- Mitigation of noise
- Harmonization with the environment
- They are inexpensive (low-cost)
- Last forever with modest maintenance
- Return completely to the earth when abandoned

Source: Akadiri, Chinyio, and Olomolaiye (2012): ‘Design of a sustainable building: A conceptual framework for implementing sustainability in the building sector.’

2.2.3. *Social sustainability*

Among the three dimensions of sustainability, the social aspect of sustainability is the hardest to implement because it is the most challenging to define and measure (Cassen 1987). Despite this challenge, there is still the need to achieve social sustainability in any community as these three dimensions of sustainability are an interrelated process that joins the physical realm with the social world. We should consider that it is very crucial to construct physical structures that create a space for better social interactions, thus leading to the achievement of a sustainable community and, this is because people use space as a vehicle of communication for regulating their contact with others (Stokols and Altman, 1987). It also helps the idea of a sustainable community.

After all, social interaction by itself is the foundation of community and society (Dempsey et al. 2011). Whereas, it is a critical factor in achieving a higher level of sustainability that leads to a successful-society along with creating a livable environment (He, Xinyi. 2018). As defined by a UK based social enterprise, specializing in place-based innovation, it is noted that ‘social sustainability helps to enhance social interactions for a community. This can be accomplished by integrating the needs, the day to day work, and lifestyle of the people, together with the creation of places that promote ‘wellbeing’ through the combination of design of the physical realm, and design of the social world

infrastructures to support social and cultural life of the community. This includes systems for citizen engagement and spaces for people and places to evolve.’ To achieve sustainability in any community or at local level, we need physical structures fundamentally functioning to facilitate the day to day activities and life style of the peoples in one neighborhood. The reason why physical structures should be provided in the community is that within these physical structures is where all the activities happen. To mention some examples, walkways, seating spaces, coffee shops, local shops, groceries, parking spaces, community gardens, and many more could be listed. Many cultures of the community are manifested in these physical structures through the day to day social life of the people.

Here in our country Ethiopia, many intangible social cultures are in an amalgamated state within the social life of the community. Among these social cultures, food culture is one of them. This long history of food culture has been kept by the Ethiopians throughout the centuries. It relates to the people’s identity; this includes their religion, tradition (Vatica Sibal. 2018). Jean-Jacques Boutaud, Anda Becut and Angelica Marinescu (2016) have stated that ‘by bringing cultural values on stage, food becomes a central identity maker; defining personality, class, lifestyle, gender roles, and relationships, from family to community, to ethnic groups or nationality changing through time and place’. However, since it is an “intangible social culture,” without a physical structure, it is unfathomable. Clearly! It should be provided with a physical structure to be in service within the community’s reach. Having this in mind and as has said previously, physical structures supplement the social activities; and Mill-houses are among these physical structures that are helping the food culture (discussed in section “Chapter 3: Contextual Background”), thus by serving as a place for the food grinding production process to take place.

2.2.3. Neglected Millhouses

Millhouses, which are among the physical structures that are actively providing grinding services within our neighborhood; are highly neglected. Here we need to saturate the idea discussed in Chapter One as the ‘physical structure of one neighborhood,’ by stating that (1) whenever we choose to create a physical structure or the built environment out of new thinking, or (2) when we alter it from an existing state and reimplement it with better functionality, and also (3) when we choose to eliminate it from existing! It always has to be in a professional process of preserving, improving and creating the required quality of built environment under the particular conditions of each community embracing nature, culture, and politics as well as the economy in support of the physical development (Chansomsak, Sant & Vale, Brenda. 2010).

The above argument helps the idea that mill houses should not be eliminated nor excluded from neighborhoods, without proper study on their subject concerning their attributes on all three. We should be considering the above three dimensions of economic, environmental, and social.

2.2.4. Cultural, economic and social attributes of Mill-houses.

Embracing the community culture is seen by mill house's participation in providing grinding services for all kinds of grains that are edible in the daily food consumption by peoples. They are side by side safekeeping the food culture of the Ethiopian community. And, if we look at the economic benefits of mills, they are the prime source of a sifted meal for the majority of low-income groups in Addis Ababa. When seen through job creation and means of employment, mill houses are a source of income for over 17,800 peoples working inside 3,565 mill-houses in the city, (if one mill employs five workers only.) However, the recent trend of construction of large-scale residential communities such as apartments, condominium housing, and real-estate projects merely excluded Millhouses from their designs and their allocation in their compounds. This trend looks like it will continue to be worsening in Addis Ababa for the future due to the structural development of the city.

Benefits of having millhouses in the neighborhood

Figure 4. Cultural, economic and social attributes of mill houses

Source: Author's construction.

2.3. Structural development of the city of Addis Ababa

Any social services within a city is affected and determined by the city's structural development. A majority numbers of the mills are located and constructed inside residential areas. But the opposite is on areas which recently developed. Under such conditions, sources from CSA shows that the city of Addis Ababa is growing and expanding with an Urban Land Expansion Rate of 3.2% per year. The reason why mill houses are plenty in numbers at older neighborhoods is because of high number of users also the availability of grinding services in the city is determined by how close the users are to a nearby mill house or it is directly related with their preference issues (trust or need towards the mill owner). And their overall space usage is determined by how much area the owner have. And As an example, during the research it was conducted to estimate how many mills were around an area of 1 sq.km or radius by taking Wesson neighborhood as an example. And the results are as follow.

2.3.1. User preference issues

In the findings from the research, customers were coming as far as from Ayat-Taffo condominium to Wosson seffer (both in Yeka Sub-city, Worreda 13) yet, more than 8 km apart. The reason for this was because of the lack of mill houses among the condominium housing neighborhoods. Such exclusions of necessary facilities for the community lead to time-consuming and unwanted hustle among customers to find milling services out of the ideal range of radius for getting similar services. As from the opinion of Ato Yemata (a millowner) has said: "Millhouses are among services that should be incorporated, in one neighborhood, located at a range of a maximum of 2km (kilometers) of radius among residential housing units". From this point of representation if a millhouse's location is much less than 2km is best for their convenience for serviceability to customers. But sadly, as the city grows and expands with condominium housing constructions, where providing a vertical housing solution is perceived as a solution for the ever-growing urban expansion. (Addis Ababa City Structure Plan, 2017-2027). But small-scale millhouses are not given enough consideration among professionals. Through the local case study, this was one finding that showed the sense of modern living is furtherly excluding such basic services from the community. Thus, this study mainly relates to the embracement of the nature, culture, and economy of the community. Meaning, that communities living in urban neighborhoods of Addis Ababa have a food culture regarded as an intangible social culture inside their social life. And millhouses are directly connected with the Ethiopian community's food culture through the process of food production, and also economically related to the majority of the population since they are commercial entities located inside the urban neighborhoods. Furtherly we will see local and international case studies to know how to navigate this potential for a sustainable community.

NUMBER OF MILL HOUSES AT WESSON NEIGHBORHOOD UNDER THE RADIUS OF 1km.

Figure. 5. L Location map of mill houses in the urban neighborhoods of Yeka sub-city, at worreda 11 and 13
Source: Author' s construction

2.4. Population, urbanization and food consumption

Addis Ababa is the country's capital and home to 25% of the country's urban population. With the current growth of urbanization, the city's population is expected to double in the coming 10 to 15 years. Recent analyses have revealed that the urban population is growing rapidly at a rate of 3.8% per annum, making it worse with unemployment and poverty both at high as 23.5% and 22% respectively. At the same time, the city center has an extremely high density (up to 30,000 people per km), concentrating around 30% of the population on 8% of the land, generally with poor living conditions and a maximum density of 30,000 people/km² Ethiopia (Urbanization Review, 2015) Along with this, the city is the fastest-growing city in Africa. Also, have a vision of becoming a middle-income economy by 2025. Addis Ababa's economy is growing annually by 14%. But the national food poverty headcount index is 33.6% on average (34.7% rural and 27.9% in urban areas).

In the Ethiopian context, it is not easy to differentiate the rural poor with the urban poor, because individuals in need of a better income and decent work migrate from the rural areas to the urban areas continuously. The increase in population creates a consumption and production unbalance where the consumption of food items becomes more than the production quantity. Concerning urban population growth migration of people to urban areas, and changes in lifestyles have a high effect on the consumption variance, as well as the choice of the government policies related to food and commercial activities with in the country. Both will have positive and negative effects on the small-scale mills.

2.5. Life style of the people

To start with the social lifestyle of the people is one good example for understanding how the physical environment in the urban area is shaped and helps to answer questions on Ethiopian food culture and the services it needs in urban areas, how much is it needed, why it is needed, and until when? (What is the next generation way of thinking about processed foods in Ethiopia? are among the primary questions to be asked. With an increasing number of health-conscious consumers across the world, an individual food consumption patterns may be affected by a number of cultural, geographic and socio-economic factors and can be used to quantify consumption patterns from the household level to the national level. Change in the lifestyle is also mainly connected to the people's ability to afford and relates to change in user's perception of food production in the city. It changes in lifestyle indicates how one family want to use a certain food item. When modernity comes and the end product users of the coming generation will relate the idea of processed food with the industrial choice and changes to their needs over food without neglecting their culture and identity.

2.7. Foreign trade in Ethiopia

Foreign trade is a major activity for Ethiopia for a growing economy. And is directly connected with the agriculture industry. As Ethiopia's policies doesn't allow to export Teff as whole meal, but as a processed food (Injera) state, mirrors the need for a modern food processing technology. This will increase the trade industry and generates income for the country as a whole. The sad truth is, in Ethiopia, like it is in other developing countries, agricultural industry is the only large industry which helps on foreign trade. Ethiopia does not have any other important producing power except for agricultural industry. That also does not meet the amount of imported industrial products. With the export income obtained from the agricultural products, it shows a chronical foreign trade deficit. This is because of the import and export unbalance.

2.8. Grains and pulses production and consumption

Teff

Here in Ethiopia, many factors affect the amount of food production in the country. Most of the reasons is connected to the technological advancement and the lower mechanization of agriculture added with underdeveloped irrigation system. However, consumption of food in Ethiopia relates to the country's own culture and naturally gifted grains in the region. For example, widely known grain that grows specific to the region of Ethiopia is Teff. The national iconic food which is consumed daily in the Ethiopian community living in the country as well as the diaspora living abroad is Injera (fermented thin bread/pancake) is mainly made from teff. For dietary requirements, Ethiopia relies on teff for two-thirds of the daily protein intake and 11% of the per capita caloric intake. Though recent studies show that Teff is mainly becoming purchased by the high-income groups in the country and due to economic differences, the low income and the destitute is consuming sorghum as an alternative grain. Regarding this, mills are seemingly working for the high-income groups. But their customers come from different size and types.

Sorghum

A widely grown grain product in Ethiopia is sorghum. And is ranked as 6th among the world's leading sorghum producers. Ethiopia has increased its sorghum production over 100% in the last 10 years. Like in corn, the production is used for the domestic consumption in sorghum. In general sorghum is becoming more consumed by the larger people in rural area and also the low-income groups in the urban area is forced to switch to sorghum as a cheaper substitute for Teff. (The Harvard Africa Policy Journal, 2013).

Corn

It is foreknown that the corn production interest in the country will increase due to having almost a parallel course of corn consumption amount in the country. It continues to increase by years and the entire production is used for the domestic consumption. Corn consumption survey data from the Central Statistics Authority (CSA) in Ethiopia shows that out of the total national production of corn, 80% was used for household consumption, 10% for sale, while the balance was used for seed, wages in kind, and animal feed. Because of lower prices compared to other grains, most of the flour mills in the rural areas mix corn with wheat to lower the price of flour. This method helps bakeries to lower the price of bread and to gain a better profit.

Wheat and barley

When compared to other grain varieties, there is a low production of Wheat and barley in the country. Yet, consumption in the country is more than the production in wheat and will continue to increase in the urban population. The wheat consumption trend in Ethiopia is gradually increasing in urban areas due to high population growth (about 2.6 percent a year), migration of people to urban areas, and changes in life styles. Because of the price escalation of teff compared to wheat and of the ease of preparation of wheat, most middle- and lower-class populations are shifting to greater wheat consumption.

Pulses

Domestic consumption amount is almost parallel with the production. Another important agricultural production field in Ethiopia is pulses. Such as Faba beans, Field peas, Haricot beans red and white, Chick-peas red and white.

2.9. Unemployment and Social Vulnerability

According to the information gained from (Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, Enhancing Urban Resilience, 2015), the city is faced with high level of poverty, unemployment, and social vulnerability. A wide range of population which is estimated 22% of the population is living below the poverty line and 29% of households in the city report having an unemployed adult (higher than the national urban average of 15%). At the same time, the city core has extremely high density (from around 15,000-30,000 people per km), concentrating around 30% of the population on 8% of the land in Addis Ababa, generally with poor living conditions. Such numbers of challenges should be taken in to consideration by making sure all societal groups have good food security, while considering of two related risks that come along with high urban population and also urban expansion.

Risks in our city

1. Urban growth,
2. Delivery of basic services

2.10. International case study

2.10.1. Prerequisites for milling services

Site selection criterion

Whenever a millhouse is planned to be constructed, the first and foremost criterion to be known is the site selection. Because the location of the building is very important but is often ignored at the beginning of constructing millhouses (Fellows, P., Axtell, B. L., & Dillon, M., 1995). Taking as a reference from the technology manual which was prepared by UNIDO for the contribution of capacity building activities on the small-scale food-processing sector in Uganda, it notes that the best location for a mill is dependent on the two factors, whether it needs to be close to customers or close to the source of raw materials. And those communities who are close to local retail markets may benefit from those who are not (UNIDO Small-scale Cereal Milling and Bakery Products, Production methods, equipment, and quality assurance practices, 2004).

The following points are from the works of Fellows, P., Axtell, B. L., & Dillon, M., (1995), and from “Small-scale Cereal Milling and Bakery Products, Production methods, equipment, and quality assurance practices, (2004)” a technology manual which was prepared by UNIDO, and each shows the criterion for site selecting of mills.

- First and foremost, the site should be located on clean ground, away from sources of insects, rodents, and smells, and the mill building should be situated in a clean area that does not have a lot of dust, waste, or stagnant water nearby.
- There should be a suitable nearby site for disposal of waste hulls and wastewater
- It should have a good supply of potable water (for sanitation and cleaning of grains, e.g.
- It should have a good supply of Electricity (depending on the type of milling machines planted in the millhouse).
- Road access is a major criterion to have access for bringing in raw materials and packaging, and sending out products is regularly important.
- Is the site situated near to the supply of raw materials? Such as grains for milling purposes.
- Are the expected markets, those which are connected with milling services easily accessible?
- The accessibility for the workers and labor availability for the required work.

The above examples are mostly related to quality aspects of the site and the highly needed considerations and prerequisites, which milling services need to acquire before going further on the planning and design processes. Among the above points, many are in considerations when seen in the context of our local case studies and also generally in the city of Addis Ababa. But as witnessed personally, their surrounding area mostly is not designed to eliminate the un proper waste disposals, the accumulation of dust and water stagnation complications seen at the nearby locations of many small-scale Millhouses in the urban neighborhoods of Addis Ababa. Such problems create dissatisfaction among customers; and the quality of processed food comes to be in question.

Figure 5. This image shows the unsuitable disposal of waste nearby millhouses, located in the inner-city neighborhoods of Addis Ababa at Yeka sub-city, woreda 11 & 13.

Source: Photographed by the author in 2020.

2.11. Considerations

Regardless of whether the mill is located in an urban or a rural area, there should be a suitable nearby site for disposal of waste hulls and wastewater. Noise and dust from the mill should not cause a nuisance to neighbours. Bakeries usually have local customers and, in contrast to flourmills, many products have a short shelf life.

A bakery should therefore be located close to customers in a busy residential or industrial area, provided smoke from ovens does not cause a nuisance to neighbours. Bakeries do not produce much waste and it can be burned or taken for disposal by local authorities.

Figure 6. Image showing the clean area (at the left) versus unclean area (at the right) for selecting the correct site for a food processing building.

Source: Fellows, P., Axtell, B. L., & Dillon, M., *Quality assurance for small-scale rural food industries* (1995, P.12)

The above image shows the differences between the two types of sites for the milling services and that the first picture resembles the needed aspects of one milling service area. It encourages the careful planning and designing of the surrounding landscape at the millhouse, along with reliable waste management that excluded the stagnant water in nearby places. Alas, the image at the right side have unsatisfactory conditions such as unclean ground surface outside of the millhouse which later will create an opportunity for unwanted mixing of toxic substances and dust particles with the processed grain; they may enter during an air inflow, holding these substances into the millhouse's working area and the grinding machines.

An alternative solution or ideally derived solution for this is that the surrounding area should be planted with grass which acts as a very efficient trap for airborne dust. For these problems and negative consequences to arise, the major problem could be linked to their small area. Many small-scale millhouses in the city of Addis Ababa are privately owned. Their owners build these mills by giving a small area inside their residential homes. Some live at the same compound, where there will be a millhouse and the living area behind the milling area. Secondly, it is where there will be the millhouse dominating all the residential property and the owner could be in charge or is who giving rent to other people working on milling business. Whichever the way it is, but as the millhouses are being located Infront of a residential house, the first thing to come in contact with is the low-quality neighborhood roads which are occupied by dust, improper management of waste and stagnant water along the sloppy road. This creates unsatisfactory surrounding for the process of milling services.

2.11.1. External appearance of the building

Externally and even internally the building should be clean and painted. Millhouses should have an appealing appearance from their external appearance of the building. Because their customers have visual assumptions which places external appearance as a key factor that influence customers to believe that the millhouse has good managements on the overall tasks of the milling services just by judging the external appearance.

Other needed aspects: professionally made nameplate.

2.11.2. Internal appearance of the building

The internal walls should be smooth plastered and painted with a water-resistant paint so that they can be washed easily. Ideally walls which are located at wet area should be tiled to about one meter (100 cm) up to one point five meter (150 cm) above ground level. There are also other desirable features in a food processing building that we should consider when designing a millhouse.

Desirable features in a food processing building

This includes the proper considerations that should be given for the bottom of the wall, where it meets the floor, should not be a right-angle joint. This is because, a right-angle joint is difficult to clean and collect dirt. Therefore, the concrete floor should be curved up to meet the wall and so provide a smooth surface that is easily cleaned. But this detail is often forgotten and not considered at most millhouses.

Detail image:

Figure 6. Image showing the desirable features around wet areas in a mill house.

Source: Author's construction.

2.12. Local Case Studies

2.12.1. Flour mills in Ethiopia

The data gained from the Miller Magazine, there were around 210 large flour mills in Ethiopia by the year 2012. Their capacity of flour production is high. But these 210 large scale mills are not included among the 3,565 small-scale millhouses in the city of Addis Ababa. Their milling services doesn't include other related food grains, pulses which the community uses for a daily consumption. Their primary objectives are only focused on the wheat grinding. Such kinds of large mills are fundamental for the food technology. And the Ethiopian statistics agency (ESA) prepares standards on their end products quality. And as the held interviews shows, that these mills are included in the category of commercial millers. They are the big companies. Regarding to small-scale millhouses the agency has not done studies and does not regulate their end product quality. But are merely expected to follow the good hygiene practice. Such issues raise the question of the food standard these mills provide. Though their customers see the grains face and they get grinding services directly in contact during grinding takes place.

Considering the above issues, it has led to the need to ask respondents and gather information regarding to their experiences with their inner-city neighborhood small-scale millhouses. This leads to a general standing ground for determining the proper milling services for the larger number of users in the urban. First it was tried to map out the reasons for satisfactions and dissatisfaction from mill house customers and later the mill owners and workers, within Addis Ababa.

Reasons of Satisfaction	Reasons of Dissatisfaction
Easily accessible	Low quality construction
Vital for the daily food consumption	Low quality of neatness and cleanliness
Affordability of services	Lack of proper waiting area (dust)
Preferability regarding to one's own food taste and choice of making food cuisines	Lack of proper air circulation
Variety of services (items of grains for grinding)	Lack of sound control
Availability of grains (serves as a food stock)	

Table 1 Summary of Reasons for Satisfaction & Dissatisfaction of Small-scale Mill-house customers
Source: Author's findings during research

Reasons of Satisfaction	Reasons of Dissatisfaction
Public Profitability	Lack of proper space for sleeping area
	Lack of good amount of space for parking
	Small amount of food storage area
	Lack of knowledge on construction technique

Table 2 Summary of Reasons for Satisfaction & Dissatisfaction of Small-scale Millowners

Source: Author's construction

During the research, an online questionnaire was conducted. The numbers of respondents were 35, and most of them were under the age of 29. This helped to determine the generations current thinking towards these small-scale mill houses.

All questions and respondents' answers are as follows.

Image 1: Age of respondents
Source: Author's construction

Image 2: Living condition of respondents

Small-Scale Mill-houses in the Urban Neighborhoods of and their sustainable application:
The case of Millhouses in Yeka Sub-city

Image 3: Family size of respondents in figures

Image 4: Place of living

Image 5: Yes or No answer of respondents for the question of "Are you an active customer of Mill-house services?"

Small-Scale Mill-houses in the Urban Neighborhoods of and their sustainable application:
The case of Millhouses in Yeka Sub-city

Image 6: How often respondents go to mill-houses?

Image 7: Answer for the question of “If you use a milling service, how many hours do you spend at a mill-house while getting services?”

Image 8. Online questionnaire respondents answer for where they buy food grains such as Teff, Wheat...etc.

Image 9. How far the location of mill house from where the respondents live

The 10th question was about questioning of what problems respondents have seen while living around mills. And was given answers of choices, such as (1) Low quality of food grains and their end products, (2) Poor hygiene and quality in the mill (e.g., mud walls, spider webs, etc.), (3) Sound problem and (4) Odor. (5) And an answer left for the respondents to fill as their encounters were. And the answers were as follow.

Image 10. How far the location of mill house from where the respondents live

The 11th question was about questions on what problems respondents have seen while getting services from mill houses. And was given answers of choices, such as (1) Narrow space and very little space for waiting, (2) Lack of parking space, (3) The presence of waste, dust, dirt, and contaminated (stagnant water) in the area, (4) And an answer left for the respondents to fill as their encounters were. And the answers were as follow.

Small-Scale Mill-houses in the Urban Neighborhoods of and their sustainable application:
The case of Millhouses in Yeka Sub-city

Image 11. Types of problems respondents have seen while getting services from mill-houses
Source: Author's construction

Image 12. Problems respondents have encountered because of the lack of mill-houses at their place
Source: Author's construction

Image 13. Have you ever thought about the interior and exterior beauty (aesthetics) of Mill-houses?
Source: Author's construction

Image 14. Yes or No answer for the question of, “Do you understand the importance of Mill-houses for their significant contribution on safekeeping our food culture?”

Image 15. Yes or No answer for the question of, “Mill-houses are believed to decrease the beauty of our city or our neighborhoods. Do you agree?”

Image 16. Answers for, “What is your stand of mills that are active in the inner-city neighborhoods of Addis Ababa?” – (1) I always trust all millhouses in their daily work, (2) I have doubt on their end products (milling services), (3) I only go to a trustworthy client (millowner) for grinding.

Image 17. Answers for, “Do you agree if there are no mill-houses located in your neighborhood or generally in Addis Ababa?” – (1) Yes! I don't agree on mill-houses being located in Addis Ababa, (2) Mill-houses should be in every neighborhood, but they need architectural upgrading, (3) I would be happy if they are changed to Industry level.

Source: Author’s construction from online questionnaires

2.13. Location of the millhouse

The location of the selected mill-house case study area is on the side of a local street (Fig. 3), located in the inner part of the neighborhood. This particular mill-house or locally known by its name as “Tolcha Meda Wofcho-bet,” is situated in front of a kindergarten school. It is separated by 6-meter street from the KG. Also, the location of this Mill-house is at the border to both Woreda 11 and Woreda 13. It is moderately a busy millhouse in the neighborhood; since it has daily customers but faces challenges of attracting customers as there are also plenty of millhouses around the area.

The reason for choosing this site, **Wosson** neighborhood as one example is because there is a criterion for finding relevant information. Plus, there are plenty of residential communities with good neighborhood character. And the number of millhouses that have a minimum of 5-20 years of age are many. Therefore, by studying these Millhouses and by taking the **Wosson** neighborhood as one example considering the above issues this thesis will be focusing on the assessment of our millhouses for urban neighborhoods. And the analysis techniques were taken to visualize the site and the internal characters of the millhouse. And in the findings, the millhouse shows a very low architectural quality where it’s current area of 120 meter-squared (m^2) of built up area do not meet the necessary standards; in order to make the customers in the community, the millowner and the workers to be satisfied. And thus, this study identified that a dwelling that respects standards for milling production process should be well provided for the urban neighborhoods of Addis Ababa.

2.13.1. Age of the millhouse

Ato Yemata said that the millhouse was constructed in 1996 E.C by an NGO before 18 years and told that he bought the property without building it. He noted that previous owners have done little development on the structure.

2.13.2. Weaknesses

The millhouse also lacks ample area for parking and has Architectural problems to be addressed, such as worker's space and standard of construction to list the least. These can be related to the situation where such privately owned millhouses have little area allowance for construction. Plus, there are unaffordability and structural inconvenience issues where local businesses such as millhouses face; which is considered as another challenge found during the case study. Another potential of the study area is that its neighbor area is for kebele microfinance working space. And there are three locally constructed workshop buildings side by side and have been an area of the wood workshop and was in practice for several years when recently they are working on the production of food products such as injera and bread to give service for the community around.

As the study conducted the results show that the millhouse owner responded with dissatisfaction on the overall Architectural character of the millhouse. This expressed the need for an innovative design solution with a convincing idea for the enhancement of the Architectural quality. Another finding was the future road construction at the property (Fig. 3). This particular millhouse is going to be located in front of a collector road after a road construction in the near future which boosts customers in the positive way. But, yet Ato Yemata's property is not in good shape and character for user engagement. There is also a dissatisfaction among customers due to the absence of well-designed waiting area, absence of proper storage area and the absence of ample space for parking.

2.13.3. Worker's Health and wellbeing:

According to the study by Dessalenge Demeke and Diresibachew W. Haile (2018), on the Assessment of Respiratory Symptoms and Pulmonary Function Status among Workers of Flour Mills in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: It shows that comparative cross-sectional study flour mill workers developed 27.7% of restrictive type and 11.1% of obstructive type of lung disorders. Percentage prevalence of respiratory symptoms was evaluated as dry cough (27.7% vs. 9.3%), productive cough (11.1% vs. 5.6%), wheeze (14.8% vs. 3.8%), and breathlessness (16.6% vs. 7.4%) in four mill workers and controls, respectively. Based on the results of the present study, occupational exposure to flour dust could cause respiratory dysfunction, thereby reducing lung efficiency.

Figure 8: Site map of the case study area, Yeka Sub-city woreda 11 at Wesson Seffer

2.13.4. Internal and external appearance of the mill surrounding

Figure 9: Fence of the millhouse

The view from outside of the mill, showing the fence and the locally constructed sloppy roof (corrugated iron sheet) and the air out let for the mill.

Figure 11: Microfinance sheds

The three microfinance workshops located side to the case study are locally constructed sheds providing services to the community with selling of Bread, Injera and another related food items.

There is also a person who is sawing clothes side to his shop-keeping job.

Tolcha-meda
Wofcho-bet
(Millhouse)

One of the three workshops for the microfinance; this particular shed function as a space for making injera and selling to the community along with a coffee area at front side.

Figure 10: Back side of the millhouse

The view from the back of the millhouse, which shows the playground side to the small river is separating the mill from the playground (Tolcha-Meda) of the neighborhood.

Figure 12: Lack of parking space

The Millowner's pickup car parked at the side of the kindergarten school's properly in front of the millhouse, due to the lack of parking space in the millhouse compound.

External appearance of the mill building cont.

The view from the entry towards the Mill, showing a woman seating (customer of the mill) on a bench that serves as a waiting area while getting service of grinding grains.

Figure 13: Entrance view towards the mill

The waste management in the millhouse is very low and not aesthetically pleasing for users.

This also goes against the criteria of a healthy food processing and the good hygiene practices.

Figure 14: Entrance view towards the mill

Entrance area is only provided like shown in the picture, which shows an old and used stone grills laying outside as an entry point over the ditch for customers.

This may imply as a simple mistake but could cause a major injury for older aged customers.

Figure 15: Entrance view towards the mill

External appearance of the mill surrounding cont.

Inside the mill, there is an area of cultivation of home-grown vegetables. This potential helps the idea of Urban agriculture, where it is advised to cultivate on area available.

Figure 16: Image showing area of cultivation inside the mill house

Figure 17: Image showing the provided shower room for the mill workers

Under such a hard-working area, shower rooms should be provided with the standard. This doesn't show a sustainable building.

Figure 18: Image showing lack of proper waste management is seen at the millhouse

Sanitation is a major criterion for food processing buildings.

External appearance of the mill surrounding cont.

This image displays the state of the mill building condition, where workers rest for meal and also sleep during the night shifts.

Another thing is that the room is side to the grinding room.

Figure 19: Image showing separated room for the mill workers.

Figure 20: Image showing the space where grinding and storage area is located

The 120-meter square area with unplanned space use in the interior space which collectively holds the Grinding area, the waiting (customer seating space) and the Storage area side by side.

Walls and the ceiling should have been smooth, non-absorbent finish and easy to clean.

Storage space must be provided to allow for the storage and separation of items that are distinct from each other such as food products, equipment and cleaning supplies.

External appearance of the mill surrounding

Figure 21: Image showing one side window

Air flow quality is among the necessary character of a sustainable building concept. Even in food processing buildings it is a criterion to have a proper air flow for the workers and also to keep the house breathing.

* All exterior doors and windows must be tight fitting (preferably self-closing) and capable of restricting the entrance of insects and rodents.

Figure 22: Image showing the milling machine and the packaging material.

Here it is necessary to note that having a flexible area is needed in the food processing area. But unless it is clean the chance of dust particles to enter in the sifted meal is high and doesn't follow the good hygiene practice.

Selection of packaging materials is also one consideration to make the service to be sustainable.

External appearance of the mill surrounding

Figure 23: Image showing birds

The concept of sustainability also deals with keeping the natural environment which also includes every living ecological aspects of the environment.

Designing by considering each thing.

Figure 24: Image showing one side window

The three locally constructed microfinance buildings have also a space dedicated to cultivating vegetations like, Carrot, maize, and cabbage side to a local road. This is one good character and potential for a sustainable community development.

Figure 25: Image showing the room where injera and bread is sold inside the microfinance bldg.

Around the area there is also the need for an active commercial activity. They prepare bread and Injera inside the microfinance buildings (Shades). Such potential can be jointly working with an innovative design of a mill house.

External appearance of the mill surrounding

Figure 26: Image showing working area

The workers space is very limited and very small which is also triggering the space for a proper movement in the mill house. This is not put in consideration where the workers go in and out of the mill, which may cause dust and other particles to enter the grain meals being grinded.

Figure 27: Image showing the height of the interior space

Room height is one of the big points to consider while designing and constructing food processing buildings. Where one mill house should have a room height of above the longer width of the ground space.

In tropical climates, overhanging roofs keep direct sunlight off the walls and out of the building. This is particularly important when grinding involves an electric milling machines, to make working conditions more comfortable. Fiber-cement tiles offer greater insulation against heat from the sun than galvanized iron sheets do,

Figure 28: Image showing lighting lines that are visible, and *Kesha* material to keep unwanted animals from entering (birds)

External appearance of the mill surrounding cont.

Image 29: Ventilation and exhaust structure of the mill.

Proper ventilation is required in all food processing buildings and must meet the requirements of the Building Codes according to their country.

This particular mill has a very low quality and cleanness over these ventilation systems, as seen in the image it is losing the structural materials almost falling.

Bright and direct lighting is required in all food grinding buildings.

In this particular mill, the height of the building is not standardized.

Notes to be taken here are that in a mill house, or any building within a concept of sustainability, should be equipped with each equipment being of commercial grade quality and preferably certified.

As being also a locally constructed mill, it should integrate the quality of materials for its interior space, and should respect the design requirements for a food processing building.

As these mills have 24/7 hours of services, the materials within should be appealing for eyes and also for the quality of end products they serve.

Image 30: Image showing the interior side of the mill at the grinding space and the connection between the exhaust and ventilation system.

CHAPTER 3

3.1. CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

3.1.1. Introduction

In Addis Ababa, there is still the culture of milling. Mostly in the urban areas where the residential units are very high in the neighborhood. For example, at **Wosson Seffer**, which is located at the Road to Kara and included in both worreda 11 and Worreda 13 of the Yeka Sub-city, millhouses are located at collector roads within 200-400 meters (very convenient for serviceability) of distance to satisfy the urban population's need for milling services. The main objective of milling is to improve the digestibility of the grain for human consumption. And the large community is still dependent on these small mills because they are the best machines for many groups of peoples in communities and to a great extent for Ethiopia as they eliminate much tedium and time-consuming labor, especially for women. The excessive loss of time and energy for the community everywhere in the country of Ethiopia was vast before the introduction of Millhouses and milling technology in the country. Particularly women, mothers, and even young females were used to exhaustively use the **Mej** stone/ **Wefcho** to grind their daily food consumption. The amount of time spent while doing so was vast. Some say that the woman gathers and sings (**Engurguro**) that each woman rhymes together by expressing their feelings to one another in a very communal way since the grinding process was a long time. This history shows the community connection and practices in the food production process of Ethiopian dishes.

In Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, millhouses evolved through a gradual change from the traditional method of Grinding using stones or locally called (**Mej / Wefcho**) to the use of water as a source of mechanism (water turbine) that will grind the grains and other crop products. Profoundly this led to the need to locate these simple machines near rivers. This is believed to have been introduced to Ethiopia in the time when the Italians occupied Addis Ababa during the reign of Emperor Haile-Selassie, where the peoples privileged for this technology were using that at that time. In the meantime, currently here in Addis Ababa, where technology boomed and the infrastructures of Electricity were being built and the increase in the use of electrical Milling machines increased! so does the opening of new millhouses near to the place where peoples lived closely.

Ethiopia is known to have a very long and rich history of a unique food culture that passed through centuries and which is still continuing to be within a constant pattern of consumption and richness making it one of world's great stand-alone cuisines. This has benefited Ethiopia with international attention to be recognized as the home of an excellent gastronomic tradition that is known by uninfluenced tradition of food culture over the centuries unlike most African countries. The complex relationship between food and society is the identity of that particular society that sustains the society's life and involves material and symbolic aspects of cultures (Lévi-Strauss, 1964, Douglas, 1966, Fischler, 1980, Beardsworth & Keil, 1997). This link between culture and food in Ethiopia can be seen by the everyday food consumptions, religious occasions and on the Ethiopian holidays. This shows the symbolic aspects of food culture in one society, meaning that our food practices, or the way we understand our relation to food is always related to our identity. Food culture is highly connected with major sectors of the society's activities, such as agriculture and trade. In these fundamental sectors, there is also the process of food production where it passes from the cultivation period to the level of consumption by the consumer.

Regarding the contribution of millhouses in the digestibility of the grain for the community consumption, the milling process has given great help. let's see the next example. In a country like Ethiopia where the cultural need for maize products is found higher in demand. Such as that flour becomes in high demand when it's a holiday in Ethiopia, not only a holiday but also for different occasions this traditional backing becomes essential to make the traditional baked bread or locally known as "Difo-Dabo or Habesha Dabo" we need sifted flour. And to have flour it's important to use the milling process. Not only this but also when we see the background of most national dishes in Ethiopia, their food processes pass through the mixing of more than a couple of ingredients, for example, Injera the most famous national dish in the country is mostly mixed with Fenugreek (Abish) for softening purpose. And before the introduction of the classical choice of food grinding choice (milling) it was too much work load for the women. To add another example let's see Berbere, the main Ethiopian dish have some ingredients which were added to the Berbere to give it a good test and each of these ingredients were to be crushed using (Mewekecha) which is still in use, but at that time using hand and the Mej stones were the only option.

In this major cycle, the choice of milling technology represents a classical example of technological choice in food processing. This includes the Millhouses that play a significant role in the milling technology plus for the food delivery process to make it edible for the consumer and to keep the shelf-lives of the agricultural products since the important consideration in the marketing of food

production is its shelf-life. And due to that, it's seen in advance to use the production of sifted meals. Sifted meal includes the milling techniques which also relates to socio-economic objectives and as well as product choice, transport costs, and supply of raw materials. [UNIDO/ILO Technical Memorandum No.6].

This comes together with another benefit of Shelf-lives of the maize for the consumption and distribution of the urban neighborhood. To illustrate this, it means that maize products lose their high-fat content from their whole meal state approximately from 3 to 4 percent as against 1 to 2 percent of fat content for a sifted meal (UNIDO 1986). Due to this, milling process is the only practical possibility to produce sifted meal (maize milling) to increase the shelf-lives of the maize to make possible of keeping stocks for an extended period, which shows that Millhouses are also serving as a grains storage while being located near residents making them easily reachable. This helps to increase the marketing chain for wholesalers and retailers, also to make possible for long-distance transportation of meals. And this becomes a major requirement in the large urban areas where flour is in high demand. It is right to argue that mill houses are very essential social services that need to be incorporated in every part of the country of Ethiopia, especially for the urban area. That is why it is said that Millhouses are among the everyday social services that are working throughout the day and even at night time due to workloads to meet the needs of the customers. These customers are each family in the neighborhood, Bakery shops, and other Local Market Shops (**Baltena**) services in the local area.

Millhouses are mostly a permanent social service where one millhouse is likely to be located at a specific place for more than a decade at a minimum. This character gives the fundamentality for the millhouses to be a basic necessity for the urban settlement in any neighborhood. In addition to this, if millhouses are carefully planned by maximizing the benefits listed above, it helps to contribute to the achievement of important socio-economic objectives such as employment generation and the saving of scarce foreign exchange (UNIDO 1986). The benefits of having millhouses are plenty. We saw that they are the physical structure that is serving the food culture of the community, their services are also connected with local facilities. They are serving as a storage area for keeping stocks for an extended period, to increase the marketing chain for users like individual family units, wholesalers and retailers. They grind food grains also to make possible for long-distance transportation of meals for these wholesalers and consumption in the urban neighborhood.

According to the information from the world population review, the capital city off Addis Ababa holds 527 square kilometers of area in Ethiopia with the population density estimated to be near 5,165 individuals per square kilometer available. And within the city Addis Ababa, where urbanization is

considered growing at the fastest rate, social structures need to be addressed through Architectural Design. Millhouses are neglected when seen in the sense of modernity. And to the bigger picture, while they are generating employment and saving scarce foreign exchange. Yet, the situation in Addis Ababa regarding the trend of construction of millhouses is kept almost the same. They are not provided with adequate parking space since they are mostly privately owned and constructed within a small area. Plus, they are in poor condition concerning their physical structure. In the inner neighborhoods of Addis Ababa, it's normal to see many millhouses with only a corrugated iron sheet construction and a near falling Wattle and daub houses functioning as milling service but uninviting appearance is what is at hand. These were once considered a convenient method of construction technique (vernacular architecture) but not given any upgrading. This doesn't show a careful Architectural design trend regarding Millhouses. Since most of the urban life is experiencing technological development throughout the infrastructures and growing more to modernity, it is advised to consider these social services to be among that modernity. And much further they have not been given a redesign consideration or innovative design and merely they function as they were first intended to be.

Their connection with social interaction is limited with a very low working area and unbalanced area for the users. Even referring to some documents there is the difference in their total floor area and the space for users waiting area is not included. But mostly they are designed as the owner prefers. And the amount of space available is mostly limited by the number of mill machines to be planted. And also, as the milling machine type varies so does the floor area of the millhouses. But, a typical commercially-operated, electricity-powered hammer mill house is suggested to measure about **42m²** of total area that includes (1) the area for the plant of the mill with electric motor, along with working area, grain feed, and bagging. (2), it is the office area and spares, (3) product storage area and (4) Grain storage area. (UNIDO 1986).

3.1.2. Historical development and change

While seeing the change and challenge through time, they are neglected physical structures of the community. But this doesn't mean that there are no experiments done on Millhouses. There are some recent exemplary private stakeholders who tried to advance this traditional millhouse service. For example, Kalkidan Belete, founder and manager of Royal Baltina, started her small business nearly 4 years ago. Her small business started grinding down and providing sifted meals of **Teff** packed in size of 5, 10 and 25-kilogram. Kalkidan Belete explained how she started her business on her company's website. (<http://royalbaltina.com/>) saying it's because of concern on food security that she began to

question “who can you hold accountable?” Then continued to question “how does the modern person buy Teff?” And in her interview with BBC Amharic, she illustrates the role her company has on facilitating modern life. " I don't want to waste my time shopping at the mall or going to the mills, which is why I created the opportunity to get the **Teff** as much as they want, " she says. This is a modern way of thinking that integrates the wholesalers, local markets and milling service together within one company which creates an opportunity for employment and also if the stores grow in number and the business expands it will reach to the foreign exporting of sifted Teff and brings foreign currency.

These kinds of privately owned businesses have good potential on their reliability of food security, and accountability since they are patented and labeled by the government. But it will take time to change the way most urban communities think towards them unless they grow to compete with millhouses and reach the inner neighborhoods, the choice left for the majority of the urban community is to use traditional millhouses near their compound. Consumers prefer to buy sifted **Teff** from a nearby local millhouse and use that for a longer period. Because it's at closer range to the residence.

To generalize it, in the present neighborhood scenario, situations on most millhouses include, lack of ample space for users, parking problems, unbalanced built up area and usage of space are very minimum compared to the number of users, improper allocation, lack of design, sound pollution, traditional construction technique and choice of materials, are major issues. These issues can be included as the comfort of the users and the Architectural standard on the physical structure of millhouses, which is mostly linked to questions of what can be done on their design with consideration to create a proper environment for serviceability to communities in the urban neighborhood.

The advantages of keeping an export ban on teff in place to favor Ethiopian consumers and protect smallholder farmers, in certain respects, are significant. One of the advantages of keeping the ban in place is that it signals that domestic food security is the Government of Ethiopia's key priority. More importantly, it communicates to the country and to the world that Ethiopia is focusing its priorities on food and nutrition security by supporting its poor consumers, for whom affordability and availability of teff is almost a non-negotiable aspect of Ethiopian life.

Exporting teff could contribute to increased malnutrition, as Ethiopians would be forced to switch to cheaper, less nutritious substitutes such as sorghum, barley, or wheat as a staple cereal in their diet. Already, the continued price increase of teff has forced many Ethiopians, primarily its rural and urban poor consumers and even teff smallholder farmers, to dilute teff injera with other cereals (table 4.2.1).

CHAPTER FOUR

4.1. Executive Summary

This study has shown the character of Millhouses in the lives of the Ethiopian people regarding their Food culture and the help millhouses provide in the process of food grinding to all peoples is regarded as a necessity for our community everywhere in the City Addis Ababa. And as the study shows this, to drive out the conclusion this paper mainly focuses on the positive aspects of having a millhouse at an urban neighborhood that have a high standard of Architectural design to meet the customers need while keeping the functions to the maximum level to be progressively growing along with the ever-changing neighborhood character of the Cities Urban life.

As the research conducted and acquired information on the lack of ample area for parking at the case study site, it led to a design alternative solution for the Millhouse, including space for parking to make access for transportation methods for grains and processed products. The other potential of the study area is that its neighbor is currently working for Kebele Microfinance workshop space. which is occupied by three locally constructed workshop structures located side by side. where they have been an area of Wood workshop and was in practice for several years when recently they are working on the production of food products such as injera and bread for the community around, yet they are actively disengaged from the neighboring Millhouse and don't seem to provide satisfying service for the community. So, with that in mind it was necessary to have an alternative design solution to solve this seemingly a small problem but is which creating an unused space in the community.

And this can be solved through a design solution that can make room for advancement of space usage and create a joint production system by integrating the Microfinance working space to function alongside the Millhouse. The two parties jointly working to attract more customers and create a feeling of belonging to the community will provide them a good business space even for the future. This is due to the potential of the site that will have a change in the neighborhood in less than a year or for a maximum of 2 years. According to the master plan of the area, it is believed that there will be a construction of a Collector road that will be built for the purpose of creating access to vehicles to be connected from one SAS road to another passing in front of the millhouse and also the Microfinance shelters, that will minimize a sum amount of area from the residential buildings located at Woreda 13 site with a 2-meter depth of entering to the houses for broader road construction. So, having this is a good potential for both parties (The Millhouse and also the Microfinance structures) in order to link with more communities that will create a sustainable community due to the use of that road in the near

future. Not only that but also the problem which was seen as bad pollution of sound and dust particles coming out of the Millhouse wouldn't be affecting the Kindergarten in front of the Millhouse. which before was 8 meters far from the millhouse now becomes 10 or more meters far from the current location due to the Master plan of the road being constructed.

4.2. Vision statement

So far as seen in the city of Addis Ababa, Millhouses have been so low and unable to be upgraded with better architectural aspects regarding space usage and construction of material. Therefore, this chapter has focused on the Millhouse which is located at the chosen study area, which is found at Wosson Seffer at the side of a local street in the inner part of the neighborhood. It is found in front of a kindergarten school which is maximum within 8-meters apart from the Millhouse. Also, this particular millhouse is located at the place of the border to both Woreda 11 and Woreda 13 in Yeka Sub-city. As the studies implicated that physical structures like the Millhouse are for the enhancement of the community's sustainability. It means to integrate the needs of the peoples, throughout their day to day work and lifestyle. Based on the Literature Review (Processing the research Methodology data collection and analysis on the physical character) the later outcome of the alternative solution for the millhouse will be one which has specific modernity and renovation to the overall millhouse function that includes a parking space for a customer waiting for a period of time while the grinding process is done inside the millhouse. And also, space for women waiting outside will be addressed architecturally. Another action on the design will focus on the storage area that is intentionally built for keeping stocks for an extended period of time to shorten the time needed for the community to acquire such grains for daily consumption use.

4.3. SWOT ANALYSIS

Below is the Strength, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) Analysis of the Millhouse at at Yeka Sub-city in Worreda 11

<p><u>Potential STRENGTHS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Located at a vibrant area where residents from both Worreda 11 & 13 boarder each other. • High number of customers compared to other near millhouses at the area. • Have a good amount of Area compared to other Millhouses at the site. • Have customers at a daily basis. And have built a good reputation for more than a decade at the community. This is a good resting issue for the food policy and customer reliance. 	<p><u>Potential WEAKNESSES</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It also lacks ample area for parking. • Unproper customer waiting space and workers space. • Cleaning and waste management is low. • Poor structure. • Low engagement with the surrounding functions in a sustainability manner.
<p><u>Potential OPPORTUNITIES</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have good electricity access and located at a T-junction road in the neighborhood. • A new road construction for new master plan at the area will give boost for the area and also the millhouse. • The availability of Injera production business to its neighboring site. Which can be regarded a boosting function. 	<p><u>Potential THREATS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The river located at the back side of the millhouse. • Lack of cooperation between the two parties. • Air and sound pollution. • Funding for the project.

Table 3 SWOT analysis
Source: Author's construction

4.4. CONCLUSION

The implications of this thesis, in general, had shown a new insight and study on the unspoken and undesirable subject of our millhouse's physical conditions in the current time, here in our urban neighborhoods. The study has amplified their strong potential for helping the sustainability of our communities at the urban neighborhood level, then later which grows into a city level. It also highlighted that millhouses have to be considered as physical structures that are engaged with the community's lifestyle on a daily basis and mirrored that they have a part in the sustainability of our community. This leads to a sound argument that currently it is highly needed to strongly look from every party of the urban livelihood to consider re-developing and enhancing the architectural aspects of millhouses in the neighborhood, by fulfilling the prerequisites of milling services and thus to discuss with each authorities who are concerned to develop an exemplary design alternative as already discussed in the study.

It is known that Ethiopia have a very long and rich history of a unique food culture that passed through centuries. And we have an obligation to continue this cycle of culture in a sound and modernized way by enhancing the architecture of small-scale millhouses for the next generation; because, they are the major service providers in the food production process of the urban life. So, the design alternative will show how to keep our neighborhood millhouses in competing with the architectural modernity and use of materials, ways of processing of grains, sustainable use of the millhouse for the community's benefit. Such as the help in the contribution of the achievement of important socio-economic objectives such as employment generation and the saving of scarce foreign exchange. So to generalize it, the alternative design solution will work on the present neighborhood scenario, situations on most millhouses including, lack of ample space for users, parking problems, unbalanced built-up area, and usage of space are very minimal compared to the number of users, improper allocation, lack of design, sound pollution, traditional construction technique and choice of materials, are major issues. These issues will be tackled architecturally on the physical structure of millhouses in order to create a proper environment for serviceability to communities in the urban neighborhood.

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Though the interview is in Amharic language, the visual explorations of the millhouses in our city can be much clearly seen in the video.

ነጃህ ሚዲያ - 2 (Nejah Media – 2), by ጁኒይድ (Junaid), *ወፍሬጭ ቤት ደስ የሚል ቆይታ ዝቅ ብሎ መስራት እንዲህ ያስደስታል ማሻሻላት – ሀላፊ ከሰብ ሀላፊ ስራ በተመጣጣኝ ዋጋ እና በደስታ ይሰሩ*, online video, viewed 08 February 2020, https://youtu.be/7VjHoA54-fs?list=LLe3s9174cdDfW_LKrCbHRcQ